

Energy-Efficient LoRaWan Communication: Real-Time Applications in Aquaculture

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Abstract—Demand for ocean-based high-quality and sustainable fish protein soared in the last decade. Unlike precision agriculture, aquaculture remains an under-equipped farming activity. The aquaculture industry has provided remarkable contributions to the Sustainable Development Goal of zero hunger based on providing animal-based protein for human consumption worldwide. The success of the aquaculture industry hinges on appropriate monitoring of key water quality indicators to ensure both animal health and optimal productivity. In this context, the present work presents a cloud-based LoRaWAN system for quasi-real-time tracking of essential water quality parameters by integrating Internet of Things (IoT) sensor devices. The proposed approach harnesses the power of Long Range (LoRa) technology — especially the LoRa Wide Area Network (LoRaWAN) protocol — to facilitate efficient, large-scale monitoring focusing on data security and scalability. With practical insights drawn from IoT system deployment at an industrially relevant aquaculture farm in Brazil, this research provides a comprehensive look into the system’s capabilities, drawbacks, and end-user feedback, offering a blueprint for future aquaculture innovations.

Index Terms—Internet of Things, LoRaWAN, Cloud-based system

I. INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture is a significant and expanding industry that remarkably contributes to the Sustainable Development Goal of Zero hunger. It has produced over 157 million tonnes of animal-based protein for human consumption worldwide in 2020 [1]. In the rapid development of marine aquaculture, the water quality is regarded as a main limiting factor [2]. Critical parameters for effective aquaculture production include water temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), salinity, turbidity, pH, and conductivity [3]. Uncontrolled water quality conditions may severely impact animal health and growth rate, impacting entire cultivation systems. Although a common practice, manual assessment of physicochemical parameters is disadvantageous to aquaculture applications in which delayed actions to control water quality account for most animal loss cases [4].

The Internet of Things (IoT) has emerged as a pivotal technology in advancing precision aquaculture [5]. With its

capacity to seamlessly connect devices and sensors, IoT has enabled the real-time monitoring and precise control of crucial parameters in aquaculture settings. From tracking water quality and temperature levels in fish farms to optimizing feeding and environmental conditions for aquatic species, IoT systems have proven instrumental in enhancing productivity and sustainability within the aquaculture industry [5]. Its adaptability to various communication protocols allows it to tailor its capabilities to specific application constraints. This versatility is critical to effectively address the unique needs and challenges of aquaculture. IoT applications demand efficient data communications, high node concentration, real-time affordability, and extended battery longevity [6]. New long-distance communication methods are being developed to support this expanding array of sensor-based functionalities inherent to the IoT. Low Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN) technologies may become an ally for monitoring physicochemical parameters within entire aquaculture applications by linking IoT sensor devices. From the LPWAN protocol family, Long Range (LoRa) technology effectively communicates a few bytes of data over the network with low-power consumption [7].

LoRa peer-to-peer offers a straightforward model on which LoRa devices communicate directly without intermediaries. In contrast, LoRa Wide Area Network (LoRaWAN) is a more intricate protocol designed to operate over LoRa modulation. It comprises a structured network involving devices, gateways, and network servers [8]. In networking, its star architecture allows the integration of thousands of devices into a single network, making it ideal for large-scale and industrial scenarios. LoRaWAN provides robust security mechanisms through end-to-end encryption, ensuring data integrity and confidentiality. It also channels information via gateways to a centralized server, bolstering application management and scalability [9]. Data availability into a central server facilitates cloud-based applications to allow real-time data monitoring for aquaculture end-users.

In this context, this study introduces an end-to-end, cloud-based LoRaWAN IoT-based system tailored to address end-user aquaculture needs and constraints for quasi-real-time water quality monitoring. It also delves into user feedback and IoT system limitations from its hands-on deployment within a

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Brazilian Integrated Multitrophic Aquaculture (IMTA) farm.

II. RELATED WORK

Aquaculture industry has grown at an annual rate of 7% to support the global demand for animal protein [1]. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a leading development trend in technology that reduces the amount of human labor and fosters an efficient economy [10]. Although IoT has been successfully applied in many fields such as medicine, agriculture, industry, security, and many others, its application to aquaculture is still in its early stages [4].

Although Internet of Things (IoT) monitoring has been used in a few cases of success, aquaculture face technology-related challenges to ensure biomass production with minimal risks [11]. IoT comprises sensors, wireless transceivers and connectivity for gathering and exchanging information between networked nodes [12], [13]. This makes IoT-related solutions a growing area of interest for the aquaculture and fisheries industries, where real-time monitoring and early warning of essential water-quality parameters are crucial for optimizing growth rates, biomass production [13], [14] and supporting decision-making processes [15].

The aquaculture sector has been considered technologically outdated [10] and frequently depend on traditional farming models that rely on user experience, lacking the capability to scientifically evaluate water quality and environmental changes [16].

While IoT-based solutions have been proposed to support aquaculture applications, there is a need for long-term experimental research to identify challenges and propose suitable solutions for effective IoT integration within industrially relevant aquaculture applications [13].

This paper enhances the comprehension of the challenges related to the quality of sensor data communication, communication range, and data volume in a compact but highly effective real-world deployment within an aquaculture facility addressing the practical and subtle challenge of a real-world pilot deployment. The potential for control and actuation in the targeted environment enables a variety of smart interventions, such as adding stabilization chemicals to the water.

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

The cloud-based LoRaWAN system based on IoT sensing devices is designed to meet IMTA needs and constraints. Figure 1 depicts LoRaWAN IoT-based architecture.

A. End-node

A survey with end-users from an IMTA located in southern Brazil provided a list of target water quality parameters for aquaculture applications. In this sense, the deployed technology aims to monitor the key physico-chemical parameters - Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Temperature, Salinity, Conductivity, Turbidity and Ph - within an IMTA farm facility located in Rio Grande – RS, Brazil. The system end-node comprises four sensors, a microcontroller, a local storage module and a LoRa

radio coupled with LoRaWAN protocol. System requirements expected by the end user include:

- Consistent water quality data;
- Real-time monitoring;
- Data transmission every 5 minutes;
- Network redundancy in case of local internet interruption.

In the proposed LoRaWAN architecture, the end-nodes are key components. Serving as an IoT-based sensing entity, they primarily collect water quality information within cultivation tanks in aquaculture facilities. Figure 2 depicts the end-node block diagram.

The end-nodes are particularly designed to operate on low power, making them suitable for remote applications where frequent battery replacement or charging might be challenging. Using the LoRa modulation technique [17], these devices transmit collected data over long distances to gateways, which then relay this information to the central network server. This capacity to function over extensive ranges with minimal energy consumption makes LoRaWAN end-nodes valuable in applications like aquaculture monitoring. End-node implementation has an STM32-based microcontroller mainboard, which integrates all the IoT prototype peripherals. The water's physico-chemical parameters are read using four Modbus sensors. A UART/Modbus converter facilitates communication between the microcontroller and the IoT sensor devices. Sensor data are stored locally on an SD Card module through the SPI protocol. Meanwhile, the LoRa radio employs a UART communication interface.

For this application, a Class A LoRa radio with native LoRaWAN 1.0.2 protocol and 64 LoRa communication channels was used. It is designed to have the lowest power consumption among the three existing LoRaWAN radio classes (A, B, and C) [17]. A Class A device receives messages from the network server (downlinks) only immediately after transmitting an uplink (data send) to the server, during which the RX1 and RX2 reception windows are open [17]. This behavior results in a Class A end-node consuming less power than classes B and C, as the device does not keep its radio active during periods on which the end-node is not sending data. From this perspective, a Class A device meets the requirements of our system.

A 3.7V and 3000mAh Li-Po battery was used to power the device for approximately two days in the event of a power outage at the location. The AC-powered end-node collects sensor measurements every 5 minutes and sends the data to a central gateway through LoRaWAN radio communication.

B. Gateway

A key component that distinguishes the LoRaWAN architecture from a LoRa peer-to-peer setup is the integration of a LoRaWAN Gateway. This device serves as an intermediary between the end-node and the network server. Its primary role is to receive packets from end-nodes and relay them to the network server. LoRaWAN gateways play an instrumental role in fostering system scalability and ensuring data security and integrity as they provide a protection layer against potential

Fig. 1. LoRaWAN system network structure.

Fig. 2. End-node prototype diagram.

data breaches or interferences. The scalability feature lies in the gateways being equipped with radios that can simultaneously monitor multiple frequencies. The present work employed an indoor gateway capable of receiving packets across eight distinct channels within the AU923 frequency band - a frequency range regulated in Brazil [7].

C. Network server

The network server role in a LoRaWAN architecture involves managing the entire infrastructure of end-nodes and gateways. Presently, the community widely adopts two open-source solutions to establish scalable LoRaWAN networks with robust security encryption: The Things Network (TTN) [18] and ChirpStack [19]. Both solutions offer seamless integration of the collected data with web database services and applications designed for end-users. For this study, we opted for the ChirpStack solution mainly because this platform provides developers with greater freedom to optimize the

solution as per requirements. Our preference for ChirpStack is anchored in its versatility and embeddable nature. Consequently, this system can be run on dedicated-purpose mini-computers.

Chirpstack provides features to integrate your platform with cloud data storage solutions. Services such as InfluxDB, HTTP and MQTT can be used [19]. At this point, we chose to use the MQTT protocol to send the data received at Chirpstack to our storage server.

D. Application server

Chirpstack directs LoRa packets (water quality sensor readings) received by the LoRaWAN gateway to an artificial intelligence data analytics platform (AIDAP), a cloud-based platform that integrates different sensors, allowing easy data access and visualisation for early alarm systems. Figure 3 demonstrates the user interface on the AIDAP platform.

Fig. 3. AIDAP user interface.

The green displays illustrate real-time water quality measurements, representing the most current data acquired by the LoRaWAN-based IoT system, subsequently relayed to the user platform. The time series, delineated in blue, delineates the historical accumulation of data amassed by the IoT device. In the context of Figure 3, a time series of temperature data from

the cultivation tank is showcased; however, this functionality extends to all other variables monitored within the scope of this system. For user convenience and further analysis, all the compiled data is readily exportable from the platform in a CSV file format.

IV. DEPLOYMENT RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The LoRaWAN IoT-based system has been deployed in the Brazilian IMTA farm - Greenhouse 5. The sensors were strategically positioned 1 m from the aeration tubes and 70 cm deep. The LoRaWAN gateway has been installed 35 meters away from the tank. Figure 4 demonstrates the system implementation at IMTA Lab. Prior to deployment, each sensor utilized underwent a rigorous calibration process to ensure compliance with the measurement and accuracy standards delineated by the IMTA Lab

Fig. 4. Brazilian IMTA LAB - Greenhouse 5. (A) System installed (yellow rectangle) on the farm; (B) System location in Green and Gateway location in Red.

Once operational, the end-to-end cloud-based system provided the collected data in real time through the end-user AIDAP application interface. Before the technology deployment, the IMTA farmers used to carry out manual physico-chemical measurements twice a day. The LoRaWAN system provided 240 sensor readings daily, significantly contributing to best-supporting aquaculture applications. The technology deployment empowered the end users to early detect and mitigate variations in critical water quality parameters. This

was facilitated through an integrated cloud-based user interface accessible on a wide range of devices (e.g. smartphones, web applications and desktop computers). Figure 5 depicts concerning variations on DO levels successfully addressed based on the LoRaWAN IoT-based technology deployment. The deployed system and user validation have been key assets in the farming facility in avoiding production loss and impacts on animal welfare. User feedback meetings guided the technology design and optimisations to meet IMTA's day-to-day needs better. Upcoming optimisations include self-powering capability and a customised alarm system.

Fig. 5. Concerning variations to Dissolved Oxygen levels successfully mitigated by the IMTA farm based on LoRaWAN IoT-based technology deployment

V. CONCLUSIONS

This case study addressed the feasibility of implementing a cloud-based end-to-end system and a IoT-based LoRaWAN network architecture to support aquaculture day-to-day activities. The system monitors the physicochemical parameters of the cultivation tanks in a representative IMTA facility in Brazil. The system delivered satisfactory results for quasi-real-time physico-chemical monitoring. It allowed early detection of parameter variations through a cloud-based platform. Immediate mitigation action was necessary to prevent impacts on aquaculture production and animal welfare. The end-to-end system optimised the data acquisition process, centralizing and standardizing the data collection. It also increased data acquisition frequency, best supporting aquaculture management. The user feedback provided valuable insights to guide technology optimization. This practical deployment could establish a few system limitations, including areas of difficult access that can lead to data communication issues (e.g. packet loss). Such limitations will be addressed in future versions system system. As future work, we intend to specify the energy consumption of the IoT system to size a solar panel to make it energy self-sufficient.

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REFERENCES

- [1] S. Hawking, *The State of World Fisheries and Aquaculture 2022: Towards Blue Transformation*. Rome: FAO, 2022.
- [2] X. Zhang, Y. Zhang, Q. Zhang, P. Liu, R. Guo, S. Jin, J. Liu, L. Chen, Z. Ma, and Y. Liu, "Evaluation and analysis of water quality of marine aquaculture area," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 17, no. 4, p. 1446, 2020.
- [3] G. A. Defe and A. Z. C. Antonio, "Multi-parameter water quality monitoring device for grouper aquaculture," in *2018 IEEE 10th International Conference on Humanoid, Nanotechnology, Information Technology, Communication and Control, Environment and Management (HNICEM)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 1–5.
- [4] M. Lafont, S. Dupont, P. Cousin, A. Vallauri, and C. Dupont, "Back to the future: Iot to improve aquaculture: Real-time monitoring and algorithmic prediction of water parameters for aquaculture needs," in *2019 Global IoT Summit (GIoTS)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [5] F. Antonucci and C. Costa, "Precision aquaculture: a short review on engineering innovations," *Aquaculture International*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 41–57, 2020.
- [6] C. Arendt, S. Böcker, and C. Wietfeld, "Data-driven model-predictive communication for resource-efficient iot networks," in *2020 IEEE 6th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [7] L. A. T. Committee, "Lorawan® specification v1.1," resources.lora-alliance.org/technical-specifications/lorawan-specification-v1-1, Octobre 2017.
- [8] A. Augustin, J. Yi, T. Clausen, and W. M. Townsley, "A study of lora: Long range & low power networks for the internet of things," *Sensors*, vol. 16, no. 9, p. 1466, 2016.
- [9] M. C. Bor, J. Vidler, and U. Roedig, "Lora for the internet of things." in *Ewsn*, vol. 16, 2016, pp. 361–366.
- [10] M. Eshwar, R. Lavanya *et al.*, "Blynk based aquaculture monitoring system using iot," *World Journal of Advanced Engineering Technology and Sciences*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 262–269, 2023.
- [11] M. Lafont, S. Dupont, P. Cousin, A. Vallauri, and C. Dupont, "Back to the future: Iot to improve aquaculture : Real-time monitoring and algorithmic prediction of water parameters for aquaculture needs," in *2019 Global IoT Summit (GIoTS)*, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [12] D. Singh, G. Tripathi, and A. J. Jara, "A survey of internet-of-things: Future vision, architecture, challenges and services," in *2014 IEEE world forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT)*. IEEE, 2014, pp. 287–292.
- [13] D. R. Prapti, A. R. Mohamed Shariff, H. Che Man, N. M. Ramli, T. Perumal, and M. Shariff, "Internet of things (iot)-based aquaculture: An overview of iot application on water quality monitoring," *Reviews in Aquaculture*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 979–992, 2022.
- [14] R. Eso, H. T. Mokui, A. Arman, L. Safiuddin, and H. Husein, "Water quality monitoring system based on the internet of things (iot) for vannamei shrimp farming," *ComTech: Computer, Mathematics and Engineering Applications*, vol. 15, no. 1, 2024.
- [15] S. Rifath, C. Xavier, S. Brindasri *et al.*, "An integrated development of iot based machine learning for data-driven travel recommendations," in *2024 International Conference on Advances in Data Engineering and Intelligent Computing Systems (ADICS)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–7.
- [16] S. Liawatimena, G. Wiranda, D. Arisandi *et al.*, "Optimizing arowana fish breeding with iot aquaculture," *Digital Zone: Jurnal Teknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi*, vol. 15, no. 1, 2024.
- [17] Semtech, "What are lora® and lorawan®?" lora-developers.semtech.com/documentation/tech-papers-and-guides/lora-and-lorawan, Septembre 2023.
- [18] T. T. Network, "We are a global collaborative internet of things ecosystem that creates networks, devices and solutions using lorawan®," <https://www.thethingsnetwork.org>, 2023, accessed by 07 April. 2024.
- [19] Chirpstack, "Chirpstack, open-source lorawan® network server," <https://www.chirpstack.io>, 2023, accessed by 07 ago. 2023.